

Effect of 1-Butyl-3-Methylimidazolium Hydroxide [Bmim]OH on the Nephrocytes of Vertebrate Model *Mus musculus*

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Abstract:

By considering the biomedical approach of green chemistry, Ionic Liquids (ILs) were known for their low vapour pressure, making them an environment friendly substitute for conventional solvents. The present investigation enlightens the impact of acute effect of orally administered IL 1-butyl 3-methylimidazolium hydroxide [Bmim]OH against kidney of *Mus musculus*. Under the experimentation, selected healthy adult animals were administered orally with a predetermined median lethal dose (LD₅₀) for 12hr. and 24 hr. exposure respectively. After completion of the exposure period, the targeted tissue was analyzed for histopathology technique and the level of lipid peroxidation was measured. Exposure-dependent tissue alterations were observed and reported

pathophysiological conditions. [Bmim]OH was not significantly affected on kidney of mice. Results obtained were interpreted for excretory mechanism and renal biology in the vertebrate experimental model *Mus musculus*.

Keywords: ILs, [Bmim]OH, LD₅₀, Nephrocytes, *Mus musculus*, MAD, lipid peroxidation.

Introduction

Toxicology refers to the study of the harmful effects of chemical or physical agents on living organism (Gallo and Doull, 1996). The toxicity of the substance is its potential for its adverse effect. These can impact on the single cell, group of cells, organ system or the whole body (Campanale et al, 2020). The degree to which a chemical compound or certain combinations of chemicals can harm an organism is known as its toxicity (Uwizeyimana et al., 2017).

ILs are ionic substances composed of an organic cation and either an organic or an inorganic anion. Encompasses a broad range of substances that were characterized by low volatility at room

temperature (Forsyth et al, 2004). According to Siddiqui et al., (2007) ILs can safely and environmentally replace conventional organic solvents. Due to their symmetry of aprotic molecular solvents and balanced chemical structure of ionic interactions, the majority of ILs are liquid at room temperature; however, there are other subclasses based on distinct structural properties (Hayes et al., 2015).

Besides this ILs have other advantages such as lack of inflammation, moderate viscosity and high polarity (Aramand et al., 2009). Most studies showed that two main factors cause toxicity of ILs: exposure time and alkyl chain length of imidazolium-based ILs (Ma et al.,

2010). ILs has attracted increasing interest as new, promising surfactants. Imidazole-based ILs have been used as surfactants in many applications related to nanotechnology, material science, and biology, especially due to their self-assembling properties and their influence on the physicochemical properties of the system in which they are dissolved (Bhadani et al., 2016). Although ILs have important industrial and commercial applications, the environmental fate and potential toxicity of most ILs are still largely unknown. Only a few preliminary reports were available on their toxicological properties. (Goncalves et al., 2021).

The toxic effects of ILs were directly related to cell membrane disruption (Bubalo et al., 2017). Long alkyl chains are often present in the cationic part of IL molecules, which means that their ability to interact with cell membranes, phospholipid bilayers, and hydrophobic domains of membrane proteins is also increased. This interaction leads to membrane rupture, physiological functions, leakage of cell contents and thus cell death (Bubalo et al., 2017). Overall, the main goal of this work was to highlight the moderate to high toxicity of ILs highlight the potential risk of their use in industrial applications, and suggest how to refine their chemical structures to reduce toxicity. It is generally accepted that ILs toxicity increases with increasing ILs concentration (Kumari et al., 2020). The most important invertebrate sensor for testing the ecotoxicity of various substances, including IL substances, crustacean *Daphnia magna* which acts as a link between bacteria and higher organisms.

In general, lipid peroxidation is the process by which oxidants, such as free radicals, target lipids that have one or more carbon-carbon double bonds, particularly polyunsaturated fatty acids (Ayala et al., 2014). The initiation-propagation-termination radical chain reaction, which is an oxidation by molecular oxygen (O₂), is the fundamental mechanism of lipid peroxidation (Porter, 1986). Lipid peroxidation is hence self-propagating and will continue until the substrate is used up or termination takes place. Lipid peroxidation is a self-sustaining process that can cause significant tissue damage, which sets it

apart from other types of free radical injury (Porter et al., 1995).

By considering the physico-chemical and biological features of ILs we decided to investigate and focus on its toxicological feature against vertebrate model *Mus musculus*.

Materials and Methods

Chemical Preparation

The synthesis of 1-butyl-3-methylimidazolium hydroxide [Bmim]OH, an IL was synthesized in the lab using a standard method (Dagde et al., 2013) and its properties were analysed using various spectroscopic techniques (Bhasme et al., 2024).

Experimental Animal

Scientifically recommended female albino mice (*Mus musculus*) of 3-4 months old and weight about 30 to 35gms were used for the present study. Animals were reared in the animal house (Reg. No. 1825/PO/EReBi/S/CPCSEA) in the Department of Zoology, Shivaji University, Kolhapur. All mice were provided with pellets and RO water and kept in standard laboratory conditions.

Organ under Study

Anatomically, kidney is the major organ in the excretory mechanism, in circulation and by metabolic point of view. It is directly exposed to toxicants like drugs, xenobiotics and chemicals etc. In total metabolic homeostasis nephrocytes play avital role in the removal of nitrogenous waste material along with harmful chemicals, some time, filtration, excretion and depuration (Radi, 2019). So, considering morphological and functional feature, we have selected the kidney as the organ under investigation.

Acute Toxicity Determination

Before experimentation, [Bmim]OH acute toxicity following a 24-hr. administration was evaluated in order to identify its lethal effect on mice. The dosage of the drug that causes 50% of the tested organisms to die is known as the lethal dose (LD₅₀) and this is how the acute toxicity has been determined. The graphic method designed

by Miller and Tainter, (1944) was used to determine the LD₅₀ values. The mice were given access to food and water two to three hours after the dose was administered.

Experimental Design and Doses

Following the estimation of [Bmim]OH LD₅₀, the mice were split up into three groups. Using oral gavage, the LD₅₀ dose (18,197 mg/kg) given to the mice in the treatment groups. The mice in the control group supplied the same amount of RO water. All animals were monitored for varying durations during the experiment, including dosage exposure for 12 and 24 hours.

Histopathological Examination

After exposure, the animals were sacrificed. Following kidney removal, a standard microtechnique was applied, and Hematoxyline-Eosin (HE) staining (Harris, 1900) was performed on 4-5 μ sections. Toxicological effects of specific IL[Bmim]OH against *Mus musculus* were observed under a microscope and interpreted as per exposure.

Lipid Peroxidation

After animals were sacrificed kidneys was removed immediately and put in a fresser for hardening. After harding tissue thawing processes were done by using mortar and pestle (equal amounts of FeCl₃, PBS and Ascorbic acid). Then homogenate was put in the cooling centrifuge (Remi) at 3000 rpm for 15 min at 4°C. The supernatant was used as an enzyme source for analysis of Lipid peroxidation. The conjugated MDA was observed at 532 nm. The measurement of MDA levels was given in nanomoles per milligram of tissue (nmol/mg tissue) (Wills, 1966).

Results

The present investigation was performed to determine the acute effect of IL 1-butyl-3-methylimidazolium Hydroxide [Bmim]OH on the excretory system, especially nephrocytes from the experimental model *Mus musculus*.

Plate No. 1

Figure 1. Histopathology of Kidney (400X). A) Kidney. B) Histology of Control Group C) Histopathology of 12 h [Bmim]OH Treated Mice Kidney. D) Histopathology of 24 h [Bmim]OH Treated Mice Kidney

Anatomy and histology of the kidney of control mice showed a regular configuration of glomeruli (G) and both proximal convoluted tubule (PCT) and distal convoluted tubule (DCT) were seen [Fig.A,B]. [Bmim]OH was administrated orally to mice for 12 and 24 hours of exposure. The kidney tissue of experimental mice showed certain pathological alterations [Fig.1 C,D].

In 12hrs. [Bmim]OH treated group, the glomerular region of the kidney, glomeruli exhibited atrophic alterations, including a widening of Bowman's capsule space with evident cell degeneration and loss of the glomerular structure indicating cell death. The enlargement of the luminal space of DCT was observed [Fig.1 C].

In 24 hrs. [Bmim]OH treated group, the Bowman's capsule space and DCT dilation increased as compared control group and 12 hrs. [Bmim]OH treated group. Blood congestion (BC) was observed [Fig.1 D].

Table 1. Lipid peroxidation activity in the kidneys of *mus musculus* following a 12 hrs. and 24 hrs. exposure to an acute dose of [Bmim]OH

Control group	12 hrs. [Bmim]OH treated group	24 hrs. [Bmim]OH treated group
4.51 ± 0.30	4.56 ± 0.88	5.57 ± 0.67**

Note: P-value: P< 0.001 Highly significant***, P< 0.01 Statistically significant**, P< 0.05 Almost significant*, P> 0.05 Non significant

Figure 2. Lipid Peroxidation (MDA Level) in Kidney of Mice *Mus musculus*

The concentration of malondialdehyde (MDA) in kidney tissues showed a elevated in the groups treated with [Bmim]OH for 12 and 24 hrs. compared to the control group (Fig. 2, Table 1). Lipid peroxidation is equal to the amount of

MDA, which produce damage to cell membrane (Wong et al.2007).

Discussion

To establish targeted organ injury associated with systematic exposure, Lietch et al. (2020) documented renal injury and hepatic effects from the methyl imidazolium IL M80I in mice. M80I was administered by intraperitoneal injection twice over the course of a 24 hour period, and histopathological changes were observed under HE stained sections. The animals in the high dose group showed prominently localized multifocal and moderate degenerations. Furthermore, hepatic degeneration and desquamation of tubule cells were indicative of necrotic alterations in the glomeruli and both the proximal and distal tubules.

Young and Colleagues, (2020) reported alterations in the gut microbiota of mice that were given oral exposure to methylimidazolium ionic liquids. The aim of this study was to investigate the effects of including two distinct methylimidazolium ionic liquids (BMI and M80I) to drinking water and exposing animals to them separately. Potential effects on the kidney and liver, the target organs, were investigated. A small proportion of animals exposed to an ionic liquid showed localized and mild degeneration in their kidney sections stained with Hematoxylin and Eosin. Additionally, hepatic degeneration and desquamation of tubule cells, specifically those from the proximal and distal tubules, were indicative of necrotic alterations.

Acute effects of chloride ionic liquid on the histological structure of the mouse liver and kidney were reported by Dumitrescu et al. (2014). The 24-hour acute toxicity test was used to assess the acute toxicity of tetrabutylammonium chloride. The histological observations demonstrated that tetrabutylammonium chloride acute exposure causes several pathological alterations in the liver and kidney. Histological sections underwent microscopic examination, which revealed glomerular compressions, nephrocyte vacuolations, thickening of the Bowman's capsule outer layer, and hypertrophies of the peri-tubular capillary network in addition to hepatocyte vacuolations.

Cypermethrin's effect on histology of liver and kidney tissue of mice was documented by Mamun et al. (2014). The forty albino mice were primarily divided into two groups: the treatment group and the control group. Ordinary poultry meal containing cypermethrin was given to the animals in three treatment groups (each group had ten animals) at varying dose levels (5, 7.5, and 10 ml/kg body weight, respectively) for varying durations depending on the number of animals in each group. The findings showed that when compared to the regular organization of their control, there was an increase in the sinusoidal space, the formation of vacuoles in hepatocytes, the congestion of blood vessels with hemorrhage in hepatic tissue, the shrinkage of glomeruli, the necrosis of renal tubules, the deletion of blood vessels, and severe congestion of the renal glomerulus along with hemorrhage in renal tissues. Authors firmly recommend for the prohibition of cypermethrin and the development of harmless pesticides for use in agriculture.

There has been no prior research conducted on the impact of IL on the process of lipid peroxidation in the kidney. The study conducted by Yu et al., (2008) examined the acute impact of [C8mim] Br IL on the antioxidant enzyme system in the liver of mice. The analysis revealed that there were no substantial alterations in the levels of lipid peroxidation within the experimental group.

Conclusion

The animals exposed to LD₅₀ of [Bmim]OH a series of histopathological alterations were found in kidney. Histological nephrons showed widening of Bowman's capsule space and prominent cellular degeneration with loss of the glomerular structure. We also observed enlargement of the luminal space in the part of DCT. The lipid peroxidation level was indicating moderate inflammation to the nephrocytes which were found dose and duration dependent, against [Bmim]OH induction.

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Conflict of Interest

There is no conflict of interest.

References

Armand, M., Endres, F., MacFarlane, D. R., Ohno, H., & Scrosati, B. (2009). Ionic-liquid materials for the electrochemical challenges of the future. *Nature materials*, 8(8), 621–629. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nmat2448>

Angell, C. A., Byrne, N., & Belieres, J. P. (2007). Parallel developments in aprotic and protic ionic liquids: physical chemistry and applications. *Accounts of chemical research*, 40(11), 1228–1236. <https://doi.org/10.1021/ar7001842>.

Bhadani, A., Misono, T., Singh, S., Sakai, K., Sakai, H., & Abe, M. (2016). Structural diversity, physicochemical properties and application of imidazolium surfactants: Recent advances. *Advances in colloid and interface science*, 231, 36–58. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.csi.2016.03.005>

Bubalo, M. C. Radošević, K., Redovniković, I. R., Slivac, I., & Srček, V. G. (2017) Toxicity mechanisms of ionic liquids. *Arhiv za higijenu rada i Toksikologiju*, 68(3), 171–179. <https://doi.org/10.1515/aiht-2017-68-2979>

C.S. Bhasme., G.S. Rashinkar, N.J. Valekar, P.S. Dhotare, K.D. Sonawane N.A. Kamble (2024). Synthesis, characterization and determination of lethal dose (LD₅₀) of 1- Butyl-3-Methylimidazolium hydroxide against *Mus musculus*.

Campanale, C., Massarelli, C., Savino, I., Locaputo, V., & Uricchio, V. F. (2020). A detailed review study on potential effects of microplastics and additives of concern on human health. *International journal of environmental research and public health*, 17(4), 1212.

Dumitrescu, G., Ciochină, L. P., Stana, L., Cretescu, I., Popescu, R., Filimon, N. M., & Voia, O. S. (2014). Acute effects of

tetrabutylammonium chloride ionic liquid on the histological structure of liver and kidney in the mouse. *Romanian Biotechnological Letters*, 19 (1), 8925–8934.

Egorova, K. S., & Ananikov, V. P. (2014). Toxicity of ionic liquids: eco(cyto)activity as complicated, but unavailable parameter for task-specific optimization. *Chem sus chem*, 7(2), 336–360. <https://doi.org/10.1002/cssc.201300459>

Forsyth, S. A., Pringle, J. M., & MacFarlane, D. R. (2004). Ionic liquids—an overview. *Australian Journal of Chemistry*, 57(2), 113–119.

Gallo, M. A., & Doull, J. (1996). History and scope of toxicology. Cassarett and Doull's Toxicology. The Basic Science of Poisons (Klassen CD, ed). 5th ed. New York: McGraw-Hill, 3–11.

Gonçalves, A. R. P., Paredes, X., Cristino, A. F., Santos, F. J. V., & Queirós, C. S. G. P. (2021). Ionic Liquids-A Review of Their Toxicity to living organisms. *International journal of molecular science*, 22(11), 5612. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijms22115612>

Harris, H. F. (1900). On the rapid conversion of haematoxylin into haematein in staining reactions. *Journal of Applied Microscopic Laboratory Methods*, 3(3), 777.

Hayes, R., Warr, G. G., & Atkin, R. (2015). Structure and nanostructure in ionic liquids. *Chemical reviews*, 115(13), 6357–6426. <https://doi.org/10.1021/cr500411q>

Joseph, K. (2023) Navigating the Pros and Cons: Advantages and Disadvantages of Ionic Liquids. *Polymer science*, 8(2).

Kumari, P., Pillai, V. V., & Benedetto, A. (2020). Mechanisms of action of ionic liquids on living cells: the state of the art. *Biophysical reviews*, 12(5), 1187–1215.

Leitch, A. C., Abdelghany, T. M., Probert, P. M., Dunn, M. P., Meyer, S. K., Palmer, J. M., Cooke, M. P., Blake, L. I., Morse, K., Rosenmai, A. K., Oskarsson, A., Bates, L., Figueiredo, R. S., Ibrahim, I., Wilson, C., Abdelkader, N. F., Jones, D. E., Blain, P. G., & Wright, M. C. (2020). The

toxicity of the methylimidazolium ionic liquids, with a focus on M8OI and hepatic effects. *Food and Chemical Toxicology*, 136, 111069.

Ma, J. M., Cai, L. L., Zhang, B. J., Hu, L. W., Li, X. Y., & Wang, J. J. (2010). Acute toxicity and effects of 1-alkyl-3-methylimidazolium bromide ionic liquids on green algae. *Ecotoxicology and environmental safety*, 73(6), 1465–1469. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoenv.2009.10.004>

Mamun, M., Illa, I., Haque, K., & Ferdousi, Z. (2014). Histological study of the effects of cypermethrin on liver and kidney tissues of mice model. *IOSR journal of pharmacy and biological sciences*, 9(5), 121-128. <https://doi.org/10.9790/3008-0952121128>

Miller, L. C., & Tainter, M. L. (1944). Estimation of LD50 and its error by means of log-probit graph paper. *Proceedings of the Society for Experimental Biology and Medicine*, 57(3), 261-264. <https://doi.org/10.3181/00379727-57-14776>

Porter, N. A. (1986). Mechanisms for the autoxidation of polyunsaturated fatty acids. *Accounts of Chemical Research*, 19(9), 262-268. <https://doi.org/10.1021/ar00129a001>

Porter, N. A., Caldwell, S. E., & Mills, K. A. (1995). Mechanisms of free radical oxidation of unsaturated lipids. *Lipids*, 30(4), 277-290. <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF02536261>

Radi Z. A. (2019). Kidney Pathophysiology, Toxicology, and Drug-Induced Injury in Drug Development. *International journal of toxicology*, 38(3), 215–227. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1091581819831701>.

Siddiqui, S. A. (2007). Synthesis and study of ionic liquids for biologically active heterocycles and asymmetric synthesis.

Thamke, V., Singh P., Pal, S., Chaudhary, M., Kumari, K., Bahadur, I., & Varma R.S., (2022) Current toxicological insights of ionic liquids on various environmental living forms. *Journal of environmental chemical engineering*, 10(2). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jece.2022.107303>

Uwizeyimana, H., Wang, M., Chen, W., & Khan, K. (2017). The eco-toxic effects of pesticide and heavy metal mixtures towards earthworms in soil. *Environmental toxicology and pharmacology*, 55, 20-29.

Wong-Ekkabut, J., Xu, Z., Triampo, W., Tang, I., Tieleman, D. and Monticelli, L. 2007. Effect of lipid peroxidation on the properties of lipid bilayers: A molecular dynamics study. *Biophysical Journal*, 93(12), 4225-4236. <https://doi.org/10.1529/biophysj.107.112565>

Welton, T. (2018). Ionic liquids: a brief history. *Biophysical Reviews*, 10(3), 691– 706. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12551-018-0419-2>

Wills, E. (1966). Mechanisms of lipid peroxide formation in animal tissues. *Biochemical Journal*, 99(3), 667–676. <https://doi.org/10.1042/bj0990667>

Young, G. R., Abdelghany, T. M., Leitch, A. C., Dunn, M. P., Blain, P. G., Lanyon, C., & Wright, M. C. (2020). Changes in the gut microbiota of mice orally exposed to methylimidazolium ionic liquids. *PloS One*, 15(3), e0229745. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0229745>

Yu, M., Li, S. M., Li, X. Y., Zhang, B. J., & Wang, J. J. (2008c). Acute effects of 1-octyl-3-methylimidazolium bromide ionic liquid on the antioxidant enzyme system of mouse liver. *Ecotoxicology and Environmental Safety*, 71(3), 903–908. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoenv.2008.02.022>